

COMPREHENSIVE MANAGEMENT OF TRAUMATIC FRACTURE IN MAXILLARY
CENTRAL INCISORS USING SOCKET SHIELD TECHNIQUE AND IMMEDIATE
IMPLANT PLACEMENT: A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Background: Traumatic dental injuries in the maxillary anterior region can significantly compromise aesthetics and function. Preservation of the alveolar ridge following extraction is essential for successful implant rehabilitation, particularly in the aesthetic zone. The socket shield technique (SST) preserves the buccal root fragment and periodontal ligament, maintaining bundle bone and soft-tissue contours. When combined with immediate implant placement and bone grafting, SST enhances the predictability of aesthetic outcomes. **Case Description:** This case report describes the management of a 21-year-old male patient with traumatic fractures of the maxillary central incisors. Tooth 11 was treated with root canal therapy and restored with a full-coverage crown. Tooth 21, deemed non-restorable, was treated by extracting the palatal root fragment while retaining the buccal root segment as a socket shield. A 4.2 × 11.5 mm implant was placed immediately in a palatal position, and the jumping gap was filled with xenograft. The implant was left unloaded during healing. After four months, successful osseointegration and dome-shaped bone retention around the coronal implant region were confirmed radiographically. Cement-retained zirconia crowns were fabricated for both teeth, achieving favourable aesthetic and functional results. **Conclusion:** The socket shield technique combined with immediate implant placement and bone grafting provides a predictable strategy for preserving ridge contour and soft-tissue aesthetics in the anterior maxilla. This biologically driven approach, along with appropriate prosthetic planning, ensures stable functional and aesthetic outcomes, even in young patients with traumatic dental injuries.

KEYWORDS: Socket shield technique, immediate implant, anterior esthetics, dental trauma, bone grafting, delayed loading, cement-retained prosthesis.

INTRODUCTION

Trauma to the maxillary anterior teeth can profoundly affect esthetics, phonetics, and function. Post-extraction ridge resorption poses a significant challenge in anterior implant rehabilitation, often compromising soft-tissue contours and the final esthetic outcome. Conventional extraction followed by delayed implant placement is associated with buccal bone resorption and gingival recession.^[5,11]

The socket shield technique (SST), introduced by Hürzeler et al.,^[1] preserves the periodontal ligament and bundle bone by retaining the buccal root fragment of the extracted tooth. This biologically driven approach

maintains the natural contour of the alveolar ridge and gingival architecture, resulting in superior soft-tissue stability when compared with conventional extraction protocols.^[3,6]

When combined with immediate implant placement and bone grafting, SST enhances aesthetic predictability in the anterior maxilla, particularly in patients with high aesthetic demands.^[2,8]

CASE REPORT

A 21-year-old male patient reported with pain and mobility in the upper front teeth. His history revealed trauma 3 months earlier, for which splinting of teeth 11

and 21 was performed, as well as a previous traumatic injury 13 years ago that had also required treatment. He currently complained of persistent pain in the upper anterior region. The patient had no significant medical history, with no diabetes, hypertension, or allergies. Dental history included splinting and pulpotomy of teeth 11 and 21. He brushed once daily and exhibited a philosophical mental attitude. Extraoral examination showed a normal facial profile, symmetrical appearance, normal TMJ function, normal mouth opening, normal lip length, and a medium smile line. Intraoral examination revealed fractures in teeth 11 and 21, with a mobile fragment associated with tooth 21; oral mucosa appeared normal and oral hygiene was fair. Based on clinical findings, tooth 11 was diagnosed with an Ellis and Davis Class IV fracture, while tooth 21 exhibited an Ellis and Davis Class VI fracture. The treatment plan included root canal therapy and full-coverage all-ceramic crown placement on tooth 11, extraction and immediate implant placement at site 21 using the socket shield technique with xenograft grafting, followed by delayed loading and delivery of a cement-retained prosthesis. CBCT examination guided 3D implant positioning, and a 4.2 × 11.5 mm implant was selected according to available bone height and anatomical considerations.

Treatment Procedure

Step 1: Endodontic and Prosthetic Management of Tooth 11

Root canal treatment of 11 was completed under rubber dam isolation. The tooth was prepared for a full-coverage crown, and a temporary shell crown was fabricated to maintain esthetics during implant healing.

Step 2: Socket Shield Technique and Immediate Implant Placement at Tooth 21

Preoperative Preparation

Local anesthesia (2% lignocaine with 1:80,000 adrenaline) was administered. Tooth 21 was deemed non-restorable. The SST-based immediate implant plan was explained, and informed consent was obtained.

Sectioning and Shield Preparation

- The tooth was decoronated at the gingival margin.
- Vertical sectioning was performed using a Tungsten Carbide Surgical Lindemann bur (1.4 mm diameter, 8 mm cutting length, FG shank).
- The palatal fragment was removed using a periosteal elevator, preserving the buccal root fragment with its PDL attachment.
- The shield thickness was maintained at **1–1.5 mm**, and reduced to **1 mm above alveolar crest**, with smooth contouring.

Implant Placement

- Osteotomy was prepared palatal to the shield to avoid any contact with the retained fragment.
- A tapered titanium implant (**4.2 × 11.5 mm**) was inserted, achieving ≥ 35 Ncm primary stability.

Bone Grafting

The jumping gap between the implant surface and the retained buccal shield was filled with particulate xenograft to support bone remodelling and maintain buccal contour stability.^[2,3,10]

Temporization

No temporization was performed on the implant.

The temporary shell crown on tooth 11 maintained esthetics during healing.

Step 3: Healing and Definitive Restoration

Postoperative medications included antibiotics and 0.12% chlorhexidine mouth rinse. Follow-ups at 1 week, 1 month, and 3 months showed satisfactory healing.

After **4 months**, clinical and radiographic examination confirmed osseointegration.

Postoperative CBCT demonstrated **dome-shaped bone retention** around the coronal implant region.

Gingival retraction was performed before impression making.

A closed-tray impression coping was placed, and a PVS impression was made.

Due to implant angulation, screw-retained prosthesis was contraindicated (buccal access), and cost constraints prevented angulated solutions.

A **cement-retained zirconia crown** for 21 and an all-ceramic crown for 11 were fabricated and cemented. Delayed loading was chosen to minimize micromovement during the critical healing phase and to enhance osseointegration, especially in the esthetic zone.^[5,11]

Final esthetic and occlusal outcomes were highly satisfactory.

Figure Legends

Figure 1: Pre-operative extraoral and intraoral images.

Figure 5: Postoperative CBCT showing dome-shaped bone formation.

Figure 2: Pre-operative CBCT and implant planning.

Figure 6: Closed-tray impression procedure.

Figure 3: Socket shield preparation steps.

Figure 7: Try-in and crown fabrication steps.

Figure 4: Immediate implant placement and bone grafting.

Figure 8: Final prosthesis—Intraoral and extraoral views.

DISCUSSION

The socket shield technique has emerged as a predictable method for alveolar ridge preservation in the esthetic zone.^[1,3] By maintaining the buccal root fragment along with its periodontal ligament, SST prevents post-extraction collapse of the buccal plate and supports peri-implant soft-tissue stability.^[6,8]

Long-term clinical and radiographic studies have demonstrated favorable volumetric and esthetic outcomes with SST-based immediate implant placement.^[3,12] Baumer *et al.* reported stable facial bone dimensions and soft-tissue contours after five years of follow-up, reinforcing the biological rationale of partial extraction therapy.^[3]

Use of xenograft material in the jumping gap further contributes to ridge preservation by limiting horizontal and vertical dimensional changes following extraction.^[10]

Prosthetic decision-making is equally critical in esthetic rehabilitation. Although screw-retained restorations are often preferred, cement-retained crowns may be indicated when implant angulation compromises screw-access emergence or when financial constraints limit advanced prosthetic components.^[4,9]

The findings of this case are consistent with previously published literature reporting high implant survival rates and excellent esthetic outcomes when SST is combined with immediate implant placement and appropriate prosthetic planning.^[7,8,12]

CONCLUSION

The socket shield technique combined with immediate implant placement, bone grafting, and delayed loading represents a biologically sound and clinically effective approach for anterior esthetic rehabilitation following trauma.^[1,3,8] Proper case selection and prosthetic planning remain essential for long-term functional and esthetic success.^[5,11]

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